

DCAT RT plan improved with a combination of VMAT one in radiotherapy of the Lung Feasibility study

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Abstract

VMAT RT plans for 14 patients with lung cancer were prepared with the traditional 60Gy /2Gy fractionation. The feasibility of treating half of the treatment fractions with DCAT method, and correcting the heterogeneity in DCAT plans with VMAT bias dose plans was investigated.

The composite plans showed low heterogeneity indices and the majority were performed with lower total MUs compared to the VMAT plans.

Introduction

During the VMAT treatments, the dose distribution is produced by moving the MLC leaves and by variation of the dose rate, while during the dynamic arc therapy (DCAT), the MLC leaves follow the shape of the PTV, and the dose rate is modulated with the arc angle. The latter provides good conformality but poor dose homogeneity in the PTV. The DCAT plans are delivered with significantly lower MUs compared with the VMAT ones.

The study aimed to improve the dose homogeneity of the DCAT radiotherapy plans with a combination of VMAT ones.

Materials and methods

Seven male and seven female lung cancer patients were selected. The PTV volume, the location, the tumor depth (SSD) the lateral chest wall thickness, and the beam setup were summarized in Table 1. VMAT, DCAT, and composite radiotherapy plans were generated with the Monaco 5.1 treatment planning system. The beam setup was: 6MV 120-220 degrees arcs from 180 degrees or 180 degrees arc from 270 degrees were applied. The prescription dose was 60Gy with 2Gy fractions. The VMAT and the DCAT plans were generated with the same beam setup and IMRT restrictions.

To improve the dose homogeneity in the PTVs, the RT planings were split into a 30Gy DCAT plan, which was completed with a 30Gy VMAT bias dose plan, as illustrated in Fig.1.

The described method intended to perform the RT treatments alternatively. First the DCAT plan is performed, followed on the next treatment session the correcting VMAT plan. The fractional and the total MUs were compared. The dose heterogeneity indices in the PTV were also examined.

The difference between the dose distributions of the 60Gy VMAT plans and the composite ones, was examined with the 3D gamma indices and gamma distributions obtained with the Verisoft v6.2

(PTW, Freiburg, Germany) software. The fractional dose distributions of the 60 Gy VMAT plans, the 30Gy DCAT base plans, and the 30Gy bias dose plans were exported from the Monaco TPS. For the 3D gamma index evaluation, the VMAT dose map as a reference one, and the sum of DCAT and the VMAT bias dose maps were loaded into the Verisoft software. The dose values of the 60 Gy VMAT map were multiplied by a factor of 2. The 3D gamma index analysis were performed with 3mm distance and 3% dose correspondence. With suppression of dose values under 90% of 4Gy. the gamma analysis was limited to the PTVs and its neighborhood. The evaluated 3D gamma indices are listed in Table 2.

	PTV Volume ccm	location		start,arc degrees	SSD cm	Chest wall thickness cm
Male	281	Right lobe	at the bifurcation	cw180,180	87,00	6,00
Male	471	Right lobe	at the bifurcation	cw180,180	87,30	4,80
Male	150	Right lobe	at the bifurcation	cw180,200	87,00	6,00
Male	936	Left upper lobe	abutting the chest wall	cw180,220	84,00	2,00
Male	306,5	Left-central	at the bifurcation	ccw180,200	86	6
Male	191	Central lesion	at the bifurcation	cw270,180	82,7	4,2
Male	180,15	Left lower lobe	abutting the chest wall	ccw180,120	92,7	7
Female	534	Rigt lobe	at the bifurcation	cw180,200	93,1	5
Female	203	Left lower lobe	abutting the chest wall	cw180,220	88,1	10,3
Female	62,3	Right lobe	abutting the chest wall	cw180,120	86,8	8,7
Female	210	Right-central	at the bifurcation	cw270,180	89,1	6,7
Female	867	Riht upper lobe	abutting the chest wall	cw180,220	90,2	6,5
Female	379	mediastinum	at the bifurcation	cw270,180	85	2
Female	213	Left lobe	at the bifurcation	ccw180,200	86,8	6,6

Table 1. The patient data

Results

Fig1. The DCAT base plan dose distribution (upper left), the correcting VMAT dose map, (middle), and the lateral dose profiles across the isocenter of patient #1. The VMAT plan dose map (lower left), the sum of the DCAT base one and the VMAT correcting one (middle), and the dose profiles.

Patient #	3Dgamma %
1	98,4
2	94,2
3	92,7
4	93
5	97,5
6	95,4
7	84,8
8	87,8
9	98,3
10	96,5
11	81
12	93,6
13	85
14	89,3

Table 2. The 3D gamma indices of the composite plans with reference of the VMAT plans, pertained to the PTVs and their' close proximity

Patient #	VMAT	DCAT	composite
1	1,03	1,13	1,04
2	1,11	1,15	1,03
3	1,04	1,08	1,04
4	1,04	1,10	1,03
5	1,03	1,16	1,03
6	1,05	1,21	1,06
7	1,13	1,21	1,06
8	1,1	1,09	1,08
9	1,04	1,13	1,03
10	1,05	1,1	1,03
11	1,09	1,19	1,06
12	1,04	1,13	1,05
13	1,05	1,17	1,05
14	1,08	1,17	1,06

Table 3. The heterogeneity indices of the VMAT, DCAT, and ones of the composite plans.

Fig.2. The heterogeneity indices of the VMAT (blue), DCAT (red), and ones of the composite RT plans (green)

The heterogeneity indices of the VMAT and ones of the composite plans, agreed within +0.01... -0,03.

Patient #	VMAT 30x2Gy	DCAT 15x2Gy	VMAT COMP 15x2Gy	SUM	ratio
1	17760	3022	13380	16402	0,92
2	26730	3045	22785	25831	0,97
3	13800	3255	10515	13770	1
4	20190	2970	9280	11260	0,56
5	13740	3345	14805	18150	1,32
6	14370	3240	10140	13380	0,93
7	24900	2910	12766	15675	0,63
8	23910	3015	11715	16755	0,7
9	21840	3075	11820	14895	0,68
10	20190	2970	9280	11260	0,89
11	23910	3015	11715	16755	0,7
12	21840	2050	11820	13870	0,63
13	14910	4005	9360	13365	1,04
14	22290	3270	13830	17100	0,67

Table 4. The MUs are to deliver the 30x2Gy fractions with the VMAT plans, with the 15x2Gy DCAT ones, and with the correcting VMAT plans. The ratio of MUs of the total composite and VMAT plans.

Fig.3. The MUs to deliver the VMAT plans, the DCAT, and the correcting VMAT plans. The total MUs of the composite plans.

The total MU-s in seven composite plans were lower, five were not significantly lower, while two were higher than MU-s in full VMAT plans.

Conclusion

To deliver the prescribed 60Gy dose alternatively with a DCAT plan followed by a correcting VMAT bias dose plan, has the advantage of shorter dose delivery the DCAT fractions. In some cases, also the total MU-s were lower, compared with the full VMAT treatments.

The dose fields in the PTV of the composite plans showed good agreement with the full VMAT plans. The low heterogeneity indices indicated, that the VMAT correcting fractions effectively improved the homogeneity in the PTV.